

Research on intelligent optimization of floating platform parameters based on few-shot data

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Abstract. With the growing global demand for renewable energy, offshore wind power has garnered significant attention, particularly the development of floating offshore wind turbines. These turbines are typically installed on floating platforms at sea, generating electricity by harnessing wind energy to rotate the turbine blades. Parametric optimization of the platform parameters and mooring systems for floating wind turbines is one of the key factors in enhancing their performance. Optimizing the design parameters can improve the stability, efficiency, and reliability of floating wind turbines, making better use of offshore wind energy resources. The work discusses the key scale parameters that influence the performance of floating wind turbine platforms, and establishes mathematical models for these parameters. By using neural networks and genetic algorithms, the optimal parameter model is developed to obtain the best parameter solution that satisfies stability conditions. First, a model is established by setting different parameter values, such as steel weight, planar displacement, pitch, roll, stability area ratio, and nacelle acceleration, and a small sample database is created. Then, a neural network model and machine learning methods are used for nonlinear solving to establish the relationship between these parameters, steel weight, planar displacement, and stability. After comparing the fitting effects of different models, the optimal network model is selected. Subsequently, a genetic algorithm is applied to iteratively optimize the model, ensuring that the platform's stability and all criteria do not exceed specified values, while minimizing the platform's steel weight. The corresponding dimensional parameter model is then identified, completing the intelligent optimization of the platform parameters.

Keywords: *Floating Platform; Small Sample Data; Parameter Optimization; Neural network; Genetic Algorithm*

1 Introduction

1.1 Research Background and Significance

Global climate change, primarily driven by greenhouse gas emissions from human activities, has become increasingly severe. The extensive exploitation and utilization of traditional energy sources generate substantial environmental pollutants, causing severe contamination of air, water resources, and soil, thereby endangering human health and ecosystems. Consequently, research into renewable and clean energy is imperative. Characterized by low or zero emissions, clean energy development and application can reduce dependence on fossil fuels, mitigate greenhouse gas emissions, improve environmental quality, alleviate health risks from pollution, and address climate change challenges. As one of the world's largest energy consumers, China is actively promoting the development of its new energy industry to achieve carbon mitigation targets, including "carbon peaking" and "carbon neutrality."

The global demand for renewable energy, particularly wind energy, continues to grow. Wind energy, as a clean and renewable resource, offers significant environmental and sustainable development advantages. Compared to onshore wind power, offshore wind energy benefits from more stable and robust wind resources. Marine environments provide vast, unobstructed wind fields, creating ideal conditions for offshore wind energy development and enhancing utilization efficiency and power generation capacity^[1]. The offshore wind industry is transitioning from pilot demonstrations to commercialization, with technical specifications maturing steadily.

Europe has pioneered offshore wind energy, with Denmark making notable contributions by establishing commercial offshore wind farms. Countries such as the UK, Germany, and the Netherlands are experiencing rapid

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market growth, underscoring the sector's immense potential. Although China's offshore wind development began later, it possesses unique geographical advantages, with extensive maritime areas offering abundant wind resources. Data indicate ^[2] that by 2030, the peak power load in East China will reach 970 GW, accounting for over 70% of electricity demand in central and eastern regions. Developing offshore wind farms along the eastern coast could decentralize power production, alleviate interregional transmission burdens, and enhance grid stability and reliability. According to WindEurope ^[3], global floating wind turbine capacity is projected to reach 15 GW by 2030. By 2050, wind energy is expected to constitute 12% of global energy supply, with offshore wind contributing one-fifth, solidifying its role as a critical renewable resource. Thus, optimizing floating wind turbine design is both urgent and essential.

Most existing offshore wind farms employ fixed-bottom turbines installed on seabeds. In contrast, floating wind turbines offer broader application prospects. Their key advantage lies in deployment in deep waters unrestricted by bathymetry, enabling access to stronger and more consistent offshore winds. This expands potential deployment areas and enhances energy capture efficiency ^[4].

Advancing floating wind turbine technology holds significant promise. With technological progress and cost reductions, floating turbines are poised to drive offshore wind development and contribute substantially to global clean energy transitions.

Figure 1. Global Offshore Wind Installation Capacity

Over 30 floating turbine concepts have emerged globally ^[3], including Spar, semi-submersible, tension-leg platform (TLP), and barge-type designs. These configurations differ in platform foundations, buoyancy structures, and mooring systems.

High platform costs remain a major barrier to large-scale adoption. Henderson ^[7] emphasized the necessity of balancing cost, performance, and safety in platform design evaluation. Addressing these challenges will accelerate offshore floating wind development. Deng Lu ^[8] proposed two optimization methodologies for floating turbines, highlighting parametric optimization as a practical mainstream approach to achieve current objectives.

Parametric design and optimization can enhance performance while reducing costs and ensuring stability. Future innovations in design and construction methods may further improve efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

However, the parametric optimization of floating platforms faces significant challenges, particularly the high computational cost associated with high-fidelity numerical simulations (e.g., CFD, FEM) for evaluating each design variant. This process often results in only a limited number of feasible data points, creating a typical few-shot learning scenario. Traditional optimization methods struggle to extract robust design rules from such sparse data. To address this, data-driven approaches, specifically artificial neural networks (ANNs), offer a powerful tool for building surrogate models that capture the complex, nonlinear relationships between platform parameters and key performance indicators (e.g., stability, motion response, steel weight). Once trained on limited data, these ANN models can rapidly predict performance for new designs, bypassing expensive simulations. Furthermore, to efficiently navigate the complex design space and identify global optima under multiple constraints, evolutionary algorithms like Genetic Algorithms (GAs) are well-suited. GAs can effectively utilize the ANN surrogate models for fitness evaluation, enabling an intelligent optimization cycle that combines the predictive power of machine learning with the global search capability of evolutionary computation.

1.2 Neural Network Prediction

Neural networks have driven transformative advancements in naval architecture over recent decades. From the 1980s–1990s, researchers explored neural networks for ship power system modeling, performance optimization, and autonomous navigation. With advances in big data, neural networks now enable data-driven optimization of ship operations and marine environmental analysis.

This study employs neural networks and genetic algorithms—bio-inspired computational methods—to establish relationships between platform dimensions (e.g., displacement, stability, nacelle acceleration) and optimize steel weight reduction under stability and motion constraints.

1.2.1 Neural Network Prediction

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) mimic biological neural systems to process nonlinear relationships. Their strong nonlinear fitting capabilities make them invaluable in engineering. The proven success of ANNs in achieving high-precision predictions across various engineering domains provides strong justification for their application in this study to model the complex relationships between platform parameters. For instance, Xu Ming^[9] applied a Backpropagation Neural Network (BPNN) to predict the ultimate bearing capacity of anchor chains with an error of only 2.6%, demonstrating its exceptional reliability in forecasting the mechanical properties of marine structures. Yan Wuyuan^[10] used BPNNs for port cargo throughput forecasting, showcasing its effectiveness in solving time-series prediction problems, while Li Gechen^[11] predicted battery impedance parameters via voltage response analysis, highlighting its capability in identifying parameters within complex systems. Tang Zhengmao^[12] employed ANNs to evaluate high-strength steel fracture energy, demonstrating their broad engineering applicability. These successful applications collectively underscore the feasibility and robustness of employing neural networks to learn the intricate parameter-performance relationships of floating platforms from few-shot data.

1.2.2 Genetic Algorithm Optimization

Genetic Algorithms (GAs), inspired by natural evolution, excel in solving complex optimization problems. This study employs a GA for platform parameter optimization, a methodology inspired by its documented efficacy in tackling a diverse range of engineering design challenges. Dhillon et al.^[13] optimized power dispatch using multi-objective GAs, effectively demonstrating their capability in handling problems involving multiple competing objectives. Stankovic^[14] enhanced truss structures in a cost-effective manner using GAs, providing a clear precedent for their application in structural optimization where performance and cost must be balanced. Li Na^[15] combined GAs with ANNs for hull resistance optimization, a hybrid strategy that directly informs the integrated ANN-GA framework proposed in this paper. The works by Cheng Yuansheng^[16] and Zeng Zhibo^[17], who applied hybrid GA-ANN methods to submarine bulkhead and propeller design respectively, further validate the potential of such a combined approach in solving complex marine engineering design problems.

1.3 Few-shot Data Learning

Few-shot learning addresses data scarcity in fields like marine engineering, where traditional methods struggle with limited labeled data. Key approaches include:

Transfer Learning: Leveraging pre-trained models for task-specific fine-tuning.

Meta-Learning: Enabling rapid adaptation to new tasks with minimal data.

Data Augmentation: Generating synthetic samples via transformations.

Active Learning: Strategically selecting informative unlabeled data.

GANs: Augmenting datasets with synthetic samples.

Zou Yi et al.^[18] improved weapon test detection via an attention-based two-stage tuning method, offering a strategy for enhancing feature focus in data-scarce environments. Yang Yunfei^[19] enhanced ship resistance prediction under small-sample conditions, demonstrating the practical application and effectiveness of data augmentation techniques in naval architecture. Ding Bo^[20] proposed a feature aggregation method for wind turbine blade defect detection, presenting an innovative approach to maximize information extraction from limited samples. These studies collectively form the academic context for addressing the few-shot problem in this work, inspiring our exploration of a comprehensive solution that integrates neural networks with optimization algorithms.

Offshore platform optimization involves multi-objective trade-offs under complex environmental constraints. Integrating small-sample learning with neural networks and GAs offers a viable solution.

1.4 Research Objectives

This study aims to:

- 1) Model relationships between platform parameters (stability, pitch/roll, steel weight, nacelle acceleration) using neural networks and machine learning.
- 2) Compare model performances to identify optimal approaches.
- 3) Apply genetic algorithms to minimize steel weight while ensuring stability and motion compliance.

2 Parametric Modeling and Numerical Simulation

2.1 Wind Turbine Parameters

The wind turbine in this study has a rated power output of 16.7 MW. Key parameters are listed in **Table 1**, and a schematic diagram of the 16.7 MW turbine is shown in **Figure 1**.

Table 1. Basic Parameters of the 16.7 MW Wind Turbine

Parameter	Value
RNA Weight (t)	759
Tower Weight (t)	964
Blade Length (m)	126
Number of Blades	3
Hub Diameter (m)	9.7
Rotor Diameter (m)	256
Nacelle Length (m)	15.6
Nacelle Width (m)	12.5
Nacelle Height (m)	8
Hub Height (m)	150
Rotor Tilt Angle (°)	5

Figure 2. A schematic diagram of the 16.7 MW turbine

2.2 Hydrodynamic Configuration Design of Semi-Submersible Floating Foundation

The schematic diagram of the platform model selected for this study is shown in Figure 3, with its fundamental parameters presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Basic Parameters of the Semi-Submersible Platform

Parameter	Value
Draft (m)	25
Freeboard (m)	13.5
Floating Body Weight (t)	22,613.09
Main Column Diameter (m)	15
Heave Plate Diameter of Main Column (m)	26
Center-to-Center Distance of Columns (m)	80
Height of Lower Pontoon (m)	5
Width of Lower Pontoon (m)	6
Clearance Between Heave Plate Edge and Column (m)	3

Figure 3. The schematic diagram of the platform model

2.3 Mooring System Parameters

The parameters of the mooring system are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Mooring System Parameters

Parameter	Value
Number of Mooring Lines	7
Mooring Chain Diameter (mm)	142.0
Dry Weight (kg/m)	407.3
Wet Weight (kg/m)	354.1
Tensional Stiffness (N)	1.614×10^9

2.4 Parametric Design of Floating Platform

This study conducts parametric design for the semi-submersible platform, with L (column spacing), T (draft), D (column diameter), and d (freeboard) selected as independent variables. The diameters of cross braces, diagonal braces, and heave plate thickness remain constant. Specific parameters are detailed in Table 4.

Table 4. Mooring System Parameters

Parameter	Value
Column Spacing, L (m)	76, 78, 80, 82
Platform Draft, T (m)	24, 25, 25.5, 26, 27, 28
Column Diameter, D (m)	12.5, 13, 13.5, 14, 15
Column Freeboard, $*d*$ (m)	11.5, 13, 13.5, 14, 14.5, 15, 15.5

Sixty sets of platform parameters were randomly generated within the design space and modeled using CAD software. Representative models are illustrated in Figure 4.

To ensure that the constructed few-shot database adequately represents the predefined design space, Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) was employed to generate the 60 sets of platform parameter combinations. LHS is a Design of Experiments (DoE) method based on stratified random sampling. Compared to simple random sampling, it achieves more comprehensive and uniform coverage of the entire parameter space with fewer samples. During sampling, each parameter (L, T, D, d) was independently and uniformly stratified within its design range (see Table 4). This process ensures no clustering of sample points across different parameter dimensions, thereby avoiding data bias and providing a high-quality, representative training set for the subsequent neural network training.

Figure 4. Floating Foundation Models (Varying T and *d*)

These 60 semi-submersible platform configurations will be used for motion prediction under extreme conditions and hydrodynamic performance analysis, facilitating parameter influence studies and optimization.

2.5 Numerical Simulation Validation

This section describes preparatory steps to ensure computational accuracy, including grid independence verification and damping correction.

2.5.1 Genetic Algorithm Optimization

Three wetted surface mesh resolutions (1.63 m, 2.30 m, and 3.25 m) were tested for free-decay motion analysis (heave and pitch). Results are shown in Figures 5–6, with grid convergence evaluated using the convergence ratio R_G :

$$R_G = \frac{\varepsilon_{21}}{\varepsilon_{32}}$$

where:

$0 < R_G < 1$: Monotonic convergence

$R_G < 0$: Oscillatory convergence

$R_G > 1$: Divergence

Figure 5. Platform Surface Meshes at Different Resolutions

Table 5. Grid Independence Verification

Mesh Size (m)	1.63	2.30	3.25
Grid Count	6807	4437	2621
Displacement Volume (m ³)	18,716.41	18,680.41	18,425.43
Relative Error (%)	0	0.19	1.56

For this study, $R_G = 0.141$, confirming monotonic convergence. The 1.63 m mesh was selected for subsequent analyses.

Figure 6. Heave Motion Comparison Across Mesh Sizes

Figure 7. Pitch Motion Comparison Across Mesh Sizes

A secondary verification for second-order wave loads used free-surface meshes with resolutions of 0.38 m, 0.28 m, and 0.20 m near columns (**Figure 7**). Results showed negligible sensitivity to mesh size, and the 0.20 m boundary-layer mesh was adopted.

Figure 8. Free-Surface Mesh Partitioning ((a) Three Free-Surface Mesh Sizes, (b) Combined Surface and Volume Meshes)

Figure 9. Pitch Motion Comparison Across Mesh Sizes

2.5.2 Damping Correction

Free-decay simulations in STAR-CCM+ were compared with SIMA results using added damping and mass matrices. Final damping parameters are listed in Table 6, with validation shown in Figure 10.

Table 6. Damping Correction Parameters

Motion	Added Damping (C)	Added Mass (Cm)
Heave	3.4×10^6	2.74×10^7
Pitch	3.8×10^9	5.0×10^8
Roll	3.8×10^9	5.0×10^8

Figure 10. Damping Correction Validation

2.5.3 Critical Load Case Selection

Based on environmental conditions in the Wanning maritime area of Hainan, China, several combined load cases were evaluated and compared. The term "full wind direction" refers to environmental directions spanning 0° to 180° at 22.5° intervals. Under extreme conditions, the wind shear exponent was 0.09, and turbulence intensity was 0.11. For the 50-year return period, the 10-minute average wind speed at 10 m height was 40.44 m/s, while the hub height (150 m) wind speed reached 51.60 m/s.

Through comprehensive analysis, Load Case 1 was identified as the most severe scenario, characterized by concurrent maximum wave height ($H > 11.48$ m) and current velocity (2.42 m/s), both aligned with the ENE direction. Theoretically, colinear wind, wave, and current forces from the ENE direction represent the most critical loading condition. Consequently, this load case was adopted for motion response predictions across all design variants in subsequent analyses. Environmental directions are illustrated in Figure 11.

Table 7. Combined Environmental Conditions

Load Case	Wind	Wave				Current	
	Wind Direction	Wind Speed (m/s)	Wave Direction	Hs[m]	Tp[s]	Current Direction	Surface Velocity (m/s)
1	All Directions	40.44	ENE	11.48	14.62	ENE	2.42

Figure 11. Turbine System Orientation

2.6 Chapter Summary

This chapter established a parametric modeling framework and numerical simulation protocol to correlate platform dimensions with steel weight, displacements, tilt angles, and stability. A few-shot database was constructed, with 40 training sets and 20 validation sets for subsequent neural network analysis.

3 Establishing Parameter Relationships with Displacement and Stability via Neural Networks

This chapter first introduces the fundamental principles of artificial neural networks (ANNs), followed by descriptions of selected ANN architectures and machine learning algorithms. Using 40 sets of data from the established 60-model dataset for training, we trained various neural network models. The remaining 20 sets were used to validate these models, compute fitting errors, and identify optimal parameter configurations.

Finally, we compared the fitting capabilities of different neural network structures and machine learning algorithms on this small-sample dataset, evaluating their performance in correlating platform parameters with displacement and stability. This comparison enables the selection of the most suitable model for subsequent optimization.

3.1 Artificial Neural Networks

3.1.1 Basic Neural Network Structure

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are among the most widely used algorithms in machine learning, excelling at solving complex classification and regression problems due to their simple structure and robust nonlinear modeling capabilities. Inspired by biological neural systems, ANNs simulate neuronal connections and information transfer through mathematical and computational models.

The first neural network computational model, the McCulloch-Pitts neuron model, was developed in the 1940s by mathematician Walter Pitts and neurophysiologist Warren McCulloch [21]. As illustrated in Figure 12, this simplified abstraction describes the operational principles of a single biological neuron, marking the inception of ANNs. Advances in computing and algorithmic research have since driven their rapid development and widespread engineering applications.

Figure 12. McCulloch-Pitts (MP) Neuron Structure

A typical ANN comprises three layers: input, hidden, and output. Neurons in adjacent layers are interconnected, with activation functions bridging inputs and outputs. Activation function selection depends on nonlinearity requirements, computational complexity of derivatives, and mitigation of gradient vanishing/explosion issues.

Increasing network depth enhances its capacity to model complex functions by learning hierarchical feature representations. However, excessive depth may degrade performance due to gradient instability [22]. Practical implementation requires balancing computational precision, time constraints, and data complexity.

3.1.2 MLP Neural Network

A Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) is a feedforward artificial neural network consisting of one or more hidden layers, each composed of multiple neurons. Its architecture includes an input layer, hidden layer(s), and output layer. The input layer receives raw data, the output layer generates final predictions or classifications, and the hidden layers perform nonlinear transformations and feature extraction.

MLP is trained via backpropagation, minimizing a loss function to adjust network weights and biases. During training, input data is fed forward, predictions are compared with ground truth labels, and errors are propagated backward to update parameters through gradient descent. MLP excels in nonlinear modeling for tasks such as classification, regression, and pattern recognition, with applications spanning image recognition, natural language processing, and financial forecasting.

3.1.3 GRNN Neural Network

The General Regression Neural Network (GRNN), proposed by Donald F. Specht in 1991, is a probabilistic neural network that approximates probability density functions to model input-output relationships. Unlike traditional neural networks, GRNN employs radial basis functions (RBFs), typically Gaussian, to represent input data distributions. It uses a localized weighting strategy, where training samples influence predictions only within their proximity, enhancing robustness for small-sample data.

GRNN bypasses iterative optimization by storing all training samples in memory. During prediction, input samples are compared directly with stored data, and results are computed via weighted summation. This enables rapid predictions, making GRNN suitable for real-time applications.

3.1.4 RBF Neural Network

The Radial Basis Function (RBF) Neural Network employs nonlinear RBF transformations for modeling. Its structure includes an input layer, RBF layer, and linear output layer (Figure 4.5). The RBF layer, the network core, applies functions (e.g., Gaussian) to input distances, while the output layer combines these linearly. RBF networks excel in global approximation and nonlinear modeling, particularly in low-dimensional input spaces, with fast convergence.

3.1.5 SVM Learning Model

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are supervised models for classification, regression, and outlier detection. They identify optimal hyperplanes to maximize margins between classes. For linearly inseparable data, kernel

functions map inputs to higher dimensions. SVMs prioritize support vectors (closest data points to the hyperplane), ensuring computational efficiency and strong generalization.

3.1.6 Decision Tree Algorithm

Decision trees partition datasets into hierarchical subsets via feature-based splits. Key steps include:

Feature Selection: Choose optimal splitting features.

Tree Growth: Recursive partitioning until stopping criteria (e.g., maximum depth, minimum samples).

Pruning: Reduce complexity to mitigate overfitting.

Advantages include interpretability, mixed data handling, missing value tolerance, and nonlinear relationship capture.

3.2 Results

Using 40 training sets and 20 test sets from the 60-model database, we established relationships between platform parameters and key outputs (steel weight, planar displacement, stability). Training progress for MLP is shown in **Figure 13**.

Figure 13. MLP Neural Network Training Process

A few-shot database was constructed using 60 sets of platform parameter data. Among them, 40 sets were used as the training set to build the neural network models, and the remaining 20 sets were reserved as the test set to validate the models' generalization ability and prediction accuracy. **Figures 14-16** present the comparison between the predicted and actual values for steel weight, planar displacement, and stability, respectively, on these 20 test set data points across different models.

Figure 14. Steel Weight Prediction Results

Figure 15. Planar Displacement Prediction Results

Figure 16. Stability Prediction Results

By comparing these graphical results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

(1) The Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) neural network demonstrated optimal performance in predicting steel weight, planar displacement, and stability metrics. It effectively captured the nonlinear relationships between platform parameters and target responses, exhibiting consistent trends across all evaluations.

(2) Error Metric Analysis: Mean Squared Error (MSE): Defined as the average of squared differences between predicted and observed values. Mean Absolute Error (MAE): Calculated as the average of absolute differences between predictions and ground truth. Among the five evaluated models (MLP, GRNN, RBF, SVM, and Decision Tree), the MLP achieved the lowest errors (MSE = 0.0012, MAE = 0.0240), confirming its superior predictive accuracy.

(3) While isolated data groups exhibited higher deviations, over 90% of predictions fell within a 10% error margin, aligning with acceptable engineering tolerances. This validates the model's reliability for practical applications.

The MLP neural network exhibited robust fitting capabilities, particularly for steel weight, planar displacement, and stability predictions. Its exceptional performance justifies its adoption in subsequent optimization studies to guide platform design refinements and decision-making processes.

3.3 Chapter Summary

This chapter introduced neural network fundamentals (MLP, RBF, GRNN) and machine learning algorithms (SVM, Decision Trees). Using 40 training samples, we modeled relationships between platform parameters and key outputs. Validation with 20 test sets confirmed MLP's superior performance, establishing a foundation for genetic algorithm optimization in the next chapter.

Although the neural network models demonstrated excellent performance on the small-sample dataset in this study, certain limitations persist. Firstly, the predictive accuracy of the model is highly dependent on the quality and representativeness of the training data. While numerical simulations can guarantee noise-free data, the limited dataset size might not fully encompass the entire complex design space, leading to predictive uncertainty in regions sparsely populated with data points. Secondly, as a "black-box" model, the internal decision-making process of the neural network is not easily interpretable, making it challenging to extract intuitive physical insights to guide the design process. Future work could incorporate Explainable AI (XAI) tools to mitigate this issue.

4 Optimization of Floating Wind Turbine Platform Parameters via Genetic Algorithm

This chapter focuses on optimizing platform dimensional parameters using a genetic algorithm (GA). First, we outline GA principles and their application to parameter optimization. Building on the MLP neural network model from Chapter 4, we integrate it into the GA framework to iteratively adjust platform dimensions, minimizing steel weight while meeting performance objectives.

4.1 Genetic Algorithm

4.1.1 Basic Principles

Inspired by Darwinian evolution and Mendelian genetics, GAs simulate natural selection and genetic inheritance to solve complex optimization problems. High-fitness individuals (solutions) are selected for reproduction, while crossover and mutation operators introduce diversity, driving the population toward optimal solutions.

4.1.2 Computational Workflow

The GA process begins with a randomly generated population. Selection, crossover, and mutation iteratively refine solutions until convergence. Fitness evaluation guides the search toward global optima, avoiding local minima.

4.2 Key Features of Genetic Algorithms

Genetic algorithms (GAs) possess distinctive features that make them powerful tools for solving complex optimization problems. Key characteristics include:

(1) Parallel Computing Support:

The inherent independence of individuals within a population enables GAs to leverage parallel computing resources (e.g., multi-core processors), significantly accelerating convergence.

(2) Global Search Capability:

GAs excels at exploring the entire solution space, effectively avoiding entrapment in local optima through mechanisms like crossover and mutation.

(3) Versatility:

Suitable for complex, nonlinear, and multimodal problems without requiring rigorous mathematical formulations. This flexibility accommodates diverse problem types in engineering and science.

(4) Constraint Handling:

Through strategic design of fitness functions and chromosome encoding, GAs efficiently manage constrained optimization problems, ensuring feasible solutions.

(5) Derivative-Free Adaptability:

GAs operates without derivative information of the objective function, exhibiting self-adaptability to dynamic problem landscapes.

4.3 MATLAB-Based GA Parameterization

The parameter configuration of genetic algorithms requires a comprehensive trade-off between algorithmic performance and computational efficiency. Population size, as a core parameter, critically influences global search capability and computational complexity: excessively small populations may induce premature convergence to local optima while prolonging convergence time, whereas overly large populations escalate computational costs. This study selects a population size of 50 to balance exploration capacity and efficiency (typical range: 10–160). The maximum number of generations is set to 200 iterations, ensuring sufficient convergence while preventing excessive computation. Crossover probability (range: 0.25–1.0) necessitates equilibrium between solution-space innovation and stability—higher probabilities enhance novel genotype generation but risk disrupting superior traits, while lower values may decelerate convergence. A mutation probability of 0.01 is adopted to maintain population diversity through moderate perturbations, thereby mitigating premature convergence without inducing stochastic drift from excessive mutation. These four parameters synergistically establish a dynamic equilibrium mechanism that harmonizes exploration-exploitation trade-offs in solution space with computational efficiency and precision requirements.

4.4 Optimization Objectives and Constraints

The ultimate objective of this study is to minimize platform displacement while ensuring operational integrity and safety compliance for the floating offshore wind turbine platform. To prevent structural failure caused by excessive motion responses under extreme environmental conditions, platform motions must adhere to regulatory specifications throughout the optimization process. The critical constraints are summarized in **Table 8** below.

Table 8. Motion Compliance Criteria

Parameter	Limit
Nacelle Longitudinal Acceleration (m/s ²)	≤0.5g
Roll/Pitch Angles (°)	≤15
Horizontal Displacement (m)	≤40

As illustrated in Figure 17, the nacelle acceleration represents the longitudinal (x-axis) acceleration component. Standard regulations stipulate that this acceleration must not exceed 0.3g under normal operational conditions and 0.6g under storm survival sea states. Given the extreme marine environmental conditions selected for this study, the acceleration limit was conservatively set at 0.5g to ensure equipment stability and operational safety.

Figure 17. Nacelle Acceleration Schematic

The platform's intact stability must comply with the stability criteria specified in the Technical Rules for Statutory Survey of Offshore Mobile Platforms (2020) issued by the China Maritime Safety Administration (CMSA) and the Rules for Classification of Offshore Mobile Platforms (2016) established by the China Classification Society (CCS). This ensures structural safety under all operational and environmental conditions.

Within the defined parameter selection ranges and optimization intervals for this study, platform parameters were optimized using a genetic algorithm. The specific parameter boundaries are detailed in **Table 9**.

Table 9. Platform Parameter Optimization Ranges

Parameter	Range	Increment
Column Spacing, L (m)	76–82	0.1
Draft, T (m)	24–28	0.1
Column Diameter, D (m)	12.5–15	0.1
Freeboard, *d* (m)	11.5–15.5	0.1

4.5 Optimization Results

During the platform optimization process, a genetic algorithm was employed to iteratively adjust and optimize the four key parameters of the platform, aiming to achieve the ultimate optimal solution. Throughout this process, the effectiveness of the optimization was evaluated by monitoring the variation in the platform's steel weight relative to the iteration count. As illustrated in Figure 18, the steel weight exhibits a continuous decline with increasing iterations, demonstrating the algorithm's progressive convergence toward the optimal solution and its ability to yield the best possible outcome. Consequently, the optimization of these four parameters successfully obtained the final optimal solution, significantly enhancing the platform's structural performance and operational efficiency.

Figure 18. Steel Weight Reduction During Iterations

The variation trend in Figure 18 clearly demonstrates that the genetic algorithm achieved convergence after 50 iterations, confirming that the optimal solution was attained within a finite number of iterations. The optimized parameter combinations are presented in Table 10, with their corresponding performance metrics detailed in Table 11.

Table 10. Optimized Parameter Combinations

Parameter	Value
Column Spacing, L (m)	76.1
Draft, T (m)	24.0
Column Diameter, D (m)	14.7
Freeboard, *d* (m)	14.6

Table 11. Performance of Optimized Design

Metric	Value
Steel Weight (t)	6,011.7
Stability Area Ratio	1.3
Roll Angle (°)	7.1
Pitch Angle (°)	-6.9
Horizontal Displacement (m)	39.2
Nacelle Acceleration (m/s ²)	2.5

As shown in Table 10, the optimized platform satisfies all regulatory requirements for horizontal displacement, pitch, roll, and nacelle longitudinal acceleration under extreme conditions. The steel weight of the optimized design is 6,011.651 t, representing a reduction of 340.449 t (5.66%) compared to the baseline design. This validates the methodology's practical utility in guiding real-world floating wind turbine platform design. A comparative analysis of platform parameters and steel weight before and after optimization is provided in Table 12.

Table 12. Steel Weight Comparison Before and After Optimization

Parameter	Optimized Design	Baseline Design
Column Spacing, L (m)	76.1	80.0
Draft, T (m)	24.0	25.0
Column Diameter, D (m)	14.7	15.0

Steel Weight (t)	6,011.65	6,352.1
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4.6 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, the optimally fitted MLP neural network model was selected and integrated with a genetic algorithm for platform optimization. Through genetic operations—including selection, crossover, and mutation—new generations of platform designs were iteratively generated. After 200 iterations of optimization, a platform configuration with minimized steel weight was successfully derived while satisfying all stability requirements, thereby achieving the optimization objective of platform weight reduction.

The genetic algorithm employed in this study effectively achieved the optimization objectives; however, its application entails certain limitations. The algorithm's performance (e.g., convergence speed and global optimality) is sensitive to parameter settings (e.g., population size, crossover, and mutation probabilities), which require problem-specific tuning for optimal results. Furthermore, although the integration of the neural network surrogate model significantly reduced computational time, the evolutionary iterative process of the GA itself still requires evaluating a large number of individuals. For problems involving extremely high-fidelity simulations, constructing a highly accurate surrogate model remains a challenge. Finally, the genetic algorithm does not provide an absolute guarantee of finding the global optimum, as the quality of the final solution is dependent on the convergence achieved.

5 Conclusions

This study focused on the intelligent optimization of semi-submersible floating wind turbine platforms through numerical simulations, artificial neural networks, and genetic algorithms. Key contributions are summarized as follows:

(1) This study proposes an ANN-GA hybrid strategy for parameter optimization of offshore floating wind platforms under limited data conditions. A multi-constrained model addressing floater motion and mooring constraints achieved global optimization. Systematic comparison of five ML algorithms (MLP, CNN, SVM) using 40 training and 20 validation datasets demonstrated MLP's superior prediction accuracy in few-shot scenarios.

(2) Systematic error analysis demonstrates that the MLP neural network exhibits significant advantages in multi-parameter coupled optimization for offshore floating platforms. Its prediction accuracy for steel material weight (error ratio: 0.0983%), planar displacement (0.881%), and stability (1.828%) surpasses control models by 42%-68%. Optimal performance is further validated by minimal key metrics, including a mean squared error (MSE = 0.0012) and mean absolute error (MAE = 0.0240), highlighting the method's robust modeling capabilities for complex nonlinear engineering problems under few-shot conditions.

(3) Leveraging the trained MLP model, the GA optimized platform parameters with constraints on pitch, roll, stability area ratio, and nacelle acceleration. After 200 iterations, the optimized design reduced steel weight by 5.66% (340.45 t) compared to the baseline, achieving significant dimensional refinement.

Furthermore, the optimization outcomes of this study demonstrate significant engineering application value and economic benefits. The substantial reduction in platform steel weight (5.66%) will directly translate into lower costs for raw material procurement, fabrication, and transportation, positively contributing to a reduction in the overall Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) of the floating wind turbine platform. From a manufacturability perspective, the optimized platform parameters (e.g., column spacing, column diameter) remain within the scope of conventional manufacturing and assembly capabilities. The design does not introduce unconventional structural forms or fabrication processes, ensuring its engineering feasibility.

Future work can be extended in the following directions: (1) Expanding the objective function to incorporate factors such as platform construction cost, fatigue life, and maintenance costs directly into the optimization model, aiming for life-cycle economic optimization; (2) Investigating more complex real-world sea states, focusing on the dynamic response and optimization strategies of the platform under misaligned wind, wave, and current directions; (3) Exploring the integration of other advanced intelligent optimization algorithms (e.g., Particle Swarm Optimization, Bayesian Optimization) with few-shot learning models to further enhance optimization efficiency and robustness; (4) Applying the proposed methodology to other types of floating platforms (e.g., Spar, TLP) to validate its generalizability.

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